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Computational analysis of mass transfer limitation in porous electrodes of solid oxide electrochemical cell

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Abstract

The limitations of mass transport at elevated temperature in porous electrodes of solid oxide cells (SOC) in conditions of significant concentration gradients of gas component is one of the key contributors to the performance operation of SOCs. Uneven and low porosity ~20% (after sintering process) affects the maximal performance and lifetime of electrodes. On the other side, high porosity (above 40%) reduces the mechanical stability of sintered SOC support layer.

Due to complex nature of the mechanism and scale of analyzed case, a detailed computational fluid dynamic (CFD) modeling of diffusion transport in porous electrode was performed in order to analyze limiting factors of the mass transport through porous media at operating conditions of SOCs. Numerical investigation supported by microstructure characterization enabled understanding and distinguishing contributing process according to their significance and impact on the overall transportation in porous structures. A set of mathematical models of diffusive mass transport were examined. In the final stage, Dusty Gas Model (DGM) and Knudsen diffusion were selected and implemented in Fluent solver for the purpose of numerical study.

The calculations done using CFD model will be verified during measurements of the pressure drop and gas composition in the flow field within the porous structures. Laboratory investigations and numerical analyses will be performed with supporting layer of SOC, fabricated in the Institute of Power Engineering in Poland. The influence of porosity will be evaluated for a set of electrodes with porosity varied in the range from 15% to 35% (after sintering process), thickness from 0.55 mm to 1 mm.

Systematic analysis of these parameters and their effects on the overall operation of SOCs allow determination of the limitations of diffusion mechanisms in porous structures at high temperature, in the regime of significant concentration gradients of gaseous components. Results of this work extend the range of optimal operating conditions for fuel cells, high temperature membranes, separators, selective sieves or porous filters.

Introduction

SOCs have ability to effectively convert electrochemically hydrocarbon fuels which are usually in gaseous state. However, it is also possible to fueled them with solid (carbon) fuels [1]. Nickel-based porous structure of anode (fuel electrode in SOFC mode) is responsible for intensification of the reactions at high temperatures (between 600°C and 1000°C). In SOFC mode three main polarizations are distinguished: activation, ohmic and diffusion [2]. The last one is strictly correlated with significant concentration gradients of gas component under high electronic load. Such operating conditions are detrimental to lifetime of SOC [3] and are classified as destructive testing. An anode is an example of porous medium which is typically characterized by porosity, tortuosity [4] and Knudsen number which is associated with the diameter of the pores. Mass transport mechanism in porous anode is approximated with different diffusion models. The most popular are Fick laws, modified Fick law, Maxwell-Stefan Model and Dusty Gas Model.

Ficks laws are one of the most willingly used [5-8]. The second Fick's law assumed that fluid is stationary in a porous fuel cell electrode and convective mass transport may be neglected [9]. Due to steady character of diffusive transport, equimolar counterdiffusion, with assumption that the concentration profile does not develop with time, the second Fick's law simplifies to the first Fick's law [10]. In case of SOFC technology, there are some restrictions which limit the applicability of Fick's law [11]. Application of the first Fick's law with incorporation of porosity and tortuosity influenced by introducing effective diffusion coefficient [12] is appropriate for binary system where delivered fuel is of 100% concentration.

Next model – Modified Fick's law is based on the assumption [13] that the factor limiting current density is surface diffusion of adsorbed fuel components to active centres of the electrochemical reaction at Triple Phase Boundary – TPB. The parameter that differs modified Fick's model from standard Fick's law is the formula of diffusion coefficient $D_{i,t}$ which incorporates influence of bulk and surface diffusion by exponential weighted average at high current densities [14]. Fitting the activation energy of adsorption and surface diffusion coefficients at zero and full surface coverage is a drawback because it cannot guarantee reliability in another reaction case. This model accurateness is determined by the compliance between values of fitted parameters and experimental data.

Maxwell-Stefan (MS) model is used to characterize diffusion in multicomponent systems where volume of single molecule of gas is negligible compered to system's volume. Maxwell-Stefan diffusivity (D_{ij}) considers concentration impact in isothermal and isobaric conditions. Standard SOFC performance conditions (close to atmospheric pressure, high temperature) are well above critical temperature of commonly used gases. In this case MS model can be simplified or solved analytically [15]. Researchers prefer to simulate with MS model diffusion in nonporous media [16]. According to Huang and Goodenough's work [17], this model is the most precise when pore size diameter is large enough to neglect Knudsen diffusion.

The last one, Dusty Gas Model (DGM) is a synthesis of previously described models: multicomponent diffusion, Knudsen diffusion and viscous flow coupled with the diffusion which triggers pressure gradient. In Dusty Gas Model porous medium is treated as large, spherical and motionless dust particles. The DGM equation is expressed by Eq. (1) [16].

$$\frac{N_i}{D_{K,i}^{eff}} + \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq i}}^n \frac{y_j N_i - y_i N_j}{D_{i,j}^{eff}} = -\frac{P \nabla y_i}{RT} - \frac{y_i}{RT} \left(1 + \frac{1}{D_{K,i}^{eff}} \frac{B_0 P}{\mu} \right) \nabla P \quad (1)$$

On the left side of Eq. (1) all quantities are expressed in molar units whereas on the right side average mass velocity was used, in order to obtain pressure gradient (based on

Darcy's law). On the cathode side of SOFC this discrepancy can be neglected because molecular masses of mixture components are similar but on the anode side it may lead to some numerical errors in simulations [18]. In this case, molecular mass of hydrogen differs significantly from any other compounds.

To simplify full form of DGM an additional assumption of constant pressure in the porous medium is often used. The comparison of published results obtained from full DGM and DGM with constant pressure assumption demonstrated that neglecting the pressure gradient does not lead to considerable errors [16-19].

1. Mathematical model

Calculations of mass transport of pure hydrogen and pure carbon dioxide through porous anode in opposite directions were conducted with use of DGM in order to include diffusive transport as well as permeation and Knudsen diffusion. The aim of numerical campaign was to perform simulations in open circuit mode and isothermal conditions in order to examine solely mass transport and to identify how this process may affect the concentration polarization during SOFC performance. Knudsen number was obtained in the range of 0.2942÷0.5528, hence the transition flow was assumed [20].

Self-developed code with Dusty Gas Model was integrated into Fluent. The overall effective diffusivity determined Bosanquet (Eq. (2) [21]) where molecular and Knudsen diffusion coefficient is expressed by Chapman-Enskog formula (Eq. (3) [21]) and Eq. (4) [21] respectively.

$$D_{z,i}^{eff} = \left(\frac{1}{D_{ij}^{eff}} + \frac{1}{D_{K,i}^{eff}} \right)^{-1} \quad (2)$$

$$D_{ij} = \frac{1,86 \cdot 10^{-7} T^{\frac{3}{2}} \left(\frac{1}{M_i} + \frac{1}{M_j} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{P \Omega_D \sigma_{ij}^2} \quad (3)$$

$$D_{K,i}^{eff} = \frac{\varepsilon}{\tau} \cdot \frac{d}{3} \sqrt{\frac{8RT}{\pi M_i}} \quad (4)$$

Porous anode was modelled by the addition of momentum source term (Eq. (5)) to the Fluent's standard fluid flow equations. Only viscous resistance term was applicable due to laminar flow. It was defined based on Darcy's law [22] and structure parameters of anode material.

$$S_i = - \left(\sum_{j=1}^3 B_{ij} \mu v_j + \sum_{j=1}^3 C_{ij} \frac{1}{2} \rho |v| v_j \right) \quad (5)$$

Furthermore, mass diffusivity coefficient was of the same value as diffusion coefficient relative to molar average velocity or volume average velocity in case of binary system [12,23].

2. Results

Co-current and counter-current – two configurations of flow design were investigated for a set of various volume flow values. The flow systematically was increased from 10 [ml/min]

to 200 [ml/min] in order to evaluate the impact of residence time in the system on the outlet concentrations.

The shorter residence time, the slower diffusion through the anode (Figure 1). Carbon dioxide requires longer residence time therefore the most noticeable changes occur for small rates, up to 60 [ml/min]. In both cases hydrogen diffuses more effectively through the porous anode to upper channel. However, counter-current variant demonstrated slower diffusion process in comparison to co-current (Figure 1 and Figure 2). Velocity at the outlet of upper channel is increasing (Figure 3) as a result of hydrogen diffusion. Counter-current flow characterizes higher velocity uniformity in system.

Figure 1 Mole fractions of hydrogen at outlets depending on the flow rate for co-current flow and counter-current flow

Figure 2 Mole fraction of hydrogen distribution for Q= 40 [ml/min] – comparison between co-current (left) and counter-current (right) flow

Figure 3 Velocity profile for $Q=40$ [ml/min] – comparison between co-current (left) and counter-current (right) flow

3. Conclusions

The aim of this work was to investigate the limitations of mass transport at elevated temperature in porous electrode of solid oxide cells (SOC). The calculations were based on the fundamental conservation laws of mass with a usage of DGM in order to include diffusive transport as well as permeation. Moreover, in DGM Knudsen diffusion was also incorporated.

Carbon dioxide reflected steam – product of electrochemical reaction. It was determined that carbon dioxide diffusion was much slower than hydrogen diffusion. The counter-current flow demonstrated the slowest mass transport process for all analyzed flows. Calculations were performed in Ansys Fluent software for open circuit conditions in order to analyze mass transport phenomena not influenced by electrochemical reaction.

Developed numerical model enables the evaluation of mass transfer impact on overall process in porous anode of solid oxide cell. Further development of model depends on validation process which is planned to perform with a usage of a set of planar 50 x 50 mm anodes of SOC, delivered by Ceramic Branch CEREL of Institute of Power Engineering.

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